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Evaluation & Impact Assessment

MONITORING TOOL FOR IMPACTS

<p>MAA Scenario</p> <p>ENGAGING & INCENTIVISING INTERROGATING CREATING ADDRESSING APPLYING</p>	
<p>When to Implement</p>	<p>Used at the beginning of interactive innovation, and iteratively throughout the project.</p>
<p>Group Size</p>	<p>Any size.</p>
<p>Level of Technical Difficulty</p>	<p>Chart interpretation and basic knowledge on project management.</p>
<p>Time Needed</p>	<p>40 minutes approx.</p>
<p>Resources Required</p>	<p>Access to a computer, tablet or phone that has MS Office package installed.</p>
<p>Clustering with Other Tools</p>	<p>Tools #1, 3.</p>

PURPOSE, BACKGROUND & LOGIC

Image source: [Roman Synkevych on Unsplash](#)

Purpose

The tool is useful to set the basis for capturing the key aspects of the initiative to monitor the expected impacts. It has been designed to reflect in a participatory way on the design of the initiative and the impacts that the initiative wants to achieve. During the application of this tool, it is possible to focus beyond the first short-term results, but to plan and estimate the process required to achieve long-term impacts. The tool allows for a more in-depth analysis of the interaction with social challenges and helps to monitor them.

Background and Logic

The impacts of an innovation initiative are linked to the changes it generates and which can be directly associated with its activities. These impacts can be internal or external: they are considered external to the initiative when changes are generated in the social, environmental, or economic environment that surrounds it; on the other hand, it is considered internal when it causes a positive change in the attitudes, knowledge, or practices of the actors that are part of it.

The satisfaction of the internal or external actors of an initiative is key to its sustainability over time. A healthy and communicative relationship between them can improve the results of the initiative and facilitate its dissemination.

It is important that the expected impacts are considered during the activities of the initiative, and not only at the end. This is because they can serve as a measure to understand if expectations are being met or if, on the contrary, an adjustment in activities is required.

This tool is designed for initiatives that want to focus on the impacts and maintain them monitored during the initiative activities. The tool should be used in a participatory way, including the core actors. This is because the process of generating the information necessary for the operation of the tool can give rise to valuable conversations and confrontations that, in themselves, are an expected result of the use of this tool.

The tool can be used at any time in the process to determine its status. However, it is advisable to do it the first time at the beginning of the initiative, to establish objectives and expectations and share them with the different actors involved. After that, its periodic use is recommended to monitor the progress of the initiative and make a self-reflective analysis of the future steps to be taken.

This tool can be used in conjunction with Tool #1 and 3, as good instruments to start planning initial actions.

Materials

- MS Excel file.

Societal Challenges

A predetermined list of some of the social challenges that exist today. There is also a space at the end of the pre-established list where, in case it is considered necessary, the user can add more challenges.

Extent of Expected Contribution

The user must include a numerical assessment that represents the level of contribution that the initiative hopes to make to the related social challenge.

Assessment must be made according to the criteria displayed on the upper side of the column. For example: Our initiative is based on reforestation, therefore, my initiative will make an expected contribution to high climate change.

Actors Involved/Required

Space where the user must reflect on those actors that are necessary for the concrete realization of the expected contribution. Identified actors should be written in this column.

For example: *To contribute to climate change, livestock producers and the country's Ministry of Environment are required and should be involved.*

Changes Expected by the Actors to Achieve the Expected Impacts

Once the necessary actors have been identified to achieve the expected contribution, the user must reflect on which are the concrete changes that must occur in the actor so that the expected contribution can be achieved. The actors that were identified as necessary can change attitudes, behaviours, or, on the other hand, acquire knowledge and/or capacity.

For example: *For our initiative to contribute to climate change, it is required that producers change their attitude towards conservation, learn about its importance, and apply specific practices. It is also necessary for the Ministry of Environment to implement bonuses for forest conservation.*

Status

A value from 1 to 100 that exemplifies the progress status of the necessary changes in the actors.

Strategy

Reflect and write what strategy to be put into practice to increase the percentage marked in the previous column. The proposed strategy must be based on three key aspects of planning: What are you going to do? How will it get done? When are you going to do it?

EXPECTED RESULTS

The main result of this tool is participatory reflection. Therefore, having filled in the tables with the information agreed between the various actors involved in the initiative is the main result of this tool. The monitoring component is generated once this exercise is performed periodically, and the results obtained are compared by analysing the deviations.

Once the values have been inserted into the 'External actors' and 'Internal actors' tab, the user can view the results through a dashboard where the values inserted about the status are displayed.

Dashboard

Once the required data have been inserted, the user must go to the "External impact results" tab to view the results obtained. In the first graph, you can visually see the status of the initiative's objectives, categorized by their level of progress. The second graph is like the first, except that it refers to the social challenges to which the initiative hopes to contribute. In this visualization, the results of both graphics are interpreted according to a colour scale from red to green, where red is the lower value, meaning that the status is undeveloped, and green is the higher value, meaning positive progress.

If the results are not displayed automatically, it will be necessary to refresh the data (Select Data > Refresh All)

Illustration 2. Screenshot of the tab "Data entry - Societal challenges" showing the colour code visualization.

